

THE ROLE OF THE LATEST TECHNOLOGIES IN THE TRANSLATION INDUSTRY

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Abstract: We can say that translation had a profound and comprehensive impact on the development of cultural consciousness, the stabilization of thoughts, the expansion of spiritual worldviews, and the processes of change in science. This article covers the role of the latest technologies in the field of translation, changes in the field of translation, a look at the history of the origin and the necessary information.

Key words: Translation, language, theory, technology, history, foreign language, skills, knowledge.

There are many scientific books in Western languages (English, French, German, Italian, Spanish) that analyze our country, society, and social problems. Some of them are very well written, some of them criticize us blindly, and some of them reveal truths that we do not know. In any case, it would be appropriate if these works were translated into Uzbek so that we Uzbeks would be aware of the works written

about us in the world, and we would know what people are saying, be it truth or slander. Now they can be read by our poor scientists who know foreign languages and are lucky enough to go abroad to do scientific work. However, due to insufficient attention to social spheres, their studies are not beneficial to our country.

Based on the above, it is possible to point out some problems in the field of translation and offer their solutions.

What needs to be done to revive the translation industry in Uzbekistan

In my opinion, the state should protect the field of translation. It would be appropriate if our country had a special policy on translation and established an organization dealing with translation, for example, the Association of Translators. In addition to coordinating and controlling the policy of our state in the field of translation, this organization is obliged to train strong translators in cooperation with famous universities, to finance the translation of necessary scientific and literary works at the expense of the money allocated by the state.

At the beginning of the 20th century, the history of translation in Uzbekistan is characterized by the fact that the translation and the original literature were not separated from each other, and the translator formed the style of the writer, that is, the same style was felt in the series of translations of the works of different writers belonging to the same translator. In this process, the issues of translation theory and practice began to emerge. Analyzing the translations of those years, it can be said that these were the years of formation of passion, artistic thinking and professionalism in translation. Translators have gone through an evolutionary stage. Initially, the goal was simply to convey the meaning of the translation, but in the following years, attention was paid to the artistry, style, and choice of words in the

translation. Based on the researches of Russian scientists A. Fyodorov, V. Komissarov, L. Barkhudarov, it was the scientist Gaybullo Salomov who formulated the theory and practice of translation into Uzbek as a science.

Along with the translators who made a great contribution to the development of Uzbek translation, translation scholars who are considered to be enthusiasts of this field began to appear.

One group of translators (J. Sharipov, Y. Polatov, M. Rasuliy, N. Vladimirova) studied the history of literary translation in Uzbekistan in their research, while the next group of scientists (G. Salomov, N. Komilov), K. Musayev, H. Karomatov, K. Karomatova, N. Vladimirova, K. Tojiev, M. Kholbekov, K. Joraev, A. Abdullajonov, L. Khojaeva, S. Shukurullaeva, F. Salimova, Y. Egamova, N. Otajonov, R. Fayzullaeva, I. Gafurov, E. Ochilov, M. Javboriev, S. Jabborov, O. Rustamov, R. Karimov, S. Ochilov) theoretical foundations of the evolutionary formation of translation principles, created major scientific studies on the improvement of the science of comparative translation studies. D. Gulomova, M. Baqoeva, S. Sirojiddinov, N. Isamuhamedova, R. Karimov, S. Q. Abilov, G. Odilova, O. H. Yusupova, about the theoretical aspects of translation methods and techniques, translation art and translator's skills in later periods. The researches of translators such as M. V. Akramjanova, D. N. Turgunpolatova came into being.

1. What are the general qualities of a good translator?

- deep knowledge of a foreign language;
- professionalism;
- being able to understand the topic being translated;

- to be able to convey the idea expressed in one language in another language close to the original;
- to have above average writing ability in TT;
- comprehensive knowledge;
- full awareness of the culture of two languages;
- depth of mind;
- attention to small details and high emotional sensitivity;
- to understand special terms in the field of translation, to have skills and experience;

2. What are the special qualities of a translator of a work of art?

- broad outlook;
- understanding the linguistic landscape of the world;
- to be able to create a poetic or prose text;
- access to the spirit of the original;
- ability to recreate the spirit of the original;
- identifying and recreating the author's style;
- patience and the ability to complete the work;
- to be able to overcome obstacles in intercultural communication;
- to have spiritual (extra-linguistic) knowledge specific to the original text;
- ability to edit text.

Interpreter skills

A translator may have an innate talent, and as a result of many years of work, the translator's skills are formed. In order to call a modern translator "skilled", the following is necessary:

1. Professional skills: It is extremely important for a translator to have ethics, that is, professional etiquette. A translator should know well what to translate and what to refuse a translation order (we will discuss this issue separately in the 4th lecture).

2. Ability to work in a team: People think that translation is an individual job. However, in the course of work, the translator communicates with representatives of various fields and creates a virtual team. Sometimes, when implementing large projects, project managers form a team of translators. Sometimes it is necessary to attract clients for translation services. Marketing and advertising can only be done by people with access. For this reason, it is important for a translator to have initiative and organizational skills.

3. Attention to small details and high emotional sensitivity: If you don't pay attention to spelling mistakes, if you have the ability to notice words, phrases or letters that fall out depending on the content of the sentence with a sharp eye, this is the profession is for you. The reason is that the spelling, methodological and minor errors made during the printing process of the original text can be transferred to the translated text.

4. Adaptation and flexibility: translation is a profession that changes frequently. A person employed as a translator has to regularly change his job depending on the volume and type of work. Based on the order, the translator should be able to change

the way of work immediately - copywriting (copying), transcription (making dictionaries and encyclopedias), editing and preparation for publication.

5. Ability to allocate time correctly: translation is a type of service that must be completed on time. In order to earn the respect and trust of the client, it is necessary to perform this task on time. If a translator does not manage his time properly, no matter how skilled he may be, he may lose his credibility with the client.

6. Writing skills: this is one of the most important factors. The translator is a professional writer. A translator must have the ability to write in a scientific, artistic, journalistic style. For this, he must have a perfect knowledge of the vocabulary, grammar and style of the translation and the original language. For foreign language translators, the purity of pronunciation is also an extremely important factor that creates a positive or negative impression in front of clients. Not being able to communicate fluently in the translated language raises doubts about whether the translation will be close to the original.

7. General knowledge: general knowledge is important for a translator. If the translator is aware of the processes taking place in the world, if he keeps reading the latest information, this may come in handy during the translation process. This is because sometimes the translation is time-consuming when printing fast editions, and sometimes it can be done through the wrong sources. For this reason, the fact that the translator has certain knowledge about the daily news and current political and social processes has a positive effect on his work.

8. Analytical knowledge: first of all, a translator should be the best reader. Before translating certain sentences, one should be able to analyze in advance how this

word, sentence, or text will reach the receiver and how it will be received. Only then the translation will be readable, the reader and the client will be satisfied.

9. Research skills: every translation is a research. The translator quickly compiles a dictionary of unfamiliar field words in the text to make translations related to a special field. He works on the meaning of each. In this process, he asks for advice from his friends, acquaintances, experts in the field, works with Internet resources and glossaries.

10. Knowledge of different fields: the more knowledge a translator has in different fields, the more he can reflect it in his resume. For example, his knowledge of law, medicine, mechanics, or his ability to enter into debates about his hobby, sports, and understand the meaning of terms related to this field can be useful in his professional career. Based on his interests, if the translator summarizes his knowledge of the fields that are close and familiar to him and summarizes the extent to which he knows them in the language of translation and searches for himself, this knowledge will add color to his professional map and he will become a broad-profile translator.

11. Curiosity: Curiosity is one of the best qualities of a translator. If a translator is curious, he works on himself, learns new and unfamiliar knowledge, creates many dictionaries of new words that he often encounters, and how to eliminate translation problems. can be searched for and satisfy the customer.

12. Literacy of knowledge of foreign languages: he reads and reads a lot in the foreign language that he translates. That is, he should be able to understand with a deep look not what is said in the text, but what is being understood. Because sometimes the presence of hidden, inner meanings in the text leads the translation to the wrong paths. Such situations can be resolved only by a translator with high

language literacy. Watching movies, listening to the radio and reading books in a foreign language will have a good effect on this. Speaking of translation, first of all, let's turn to its history. The history of translation includes very long historical periods called the Old World, the Middle Ages, the New and the Most Recent. From ancient times to the present day, the Mediterranean basin of the Earth, the peoples living between the two rivers in the East, i.e. the Sumerians, Syrians, Babylonians, Assyrians, Hittites, Egypt, Iran, India, China, Turanian countries are the same. over time, it has developed as a means of social and cultural communication, as well as a type and network of written literature. In the most ancient times, that is, in the III-I centuries BC, the Roman civilization rose on Earth. Of course, the skill of the translator stands out in the rise. After Rome became an empire, it began to master the Eastern countries. Translations, book publishing, book trade, and the opening of public libraries became widespread, along with the increase in the level of literacy of the people, translation of books from one language to another, and engagement in the field of translation became more and more popular. We can say that Homer's epics were translated into Latin as a huge turning point. From the Hebrew-Aramaic copy of the first five sacred books of the Torah, the interpretation of seventy commentaries was translated into Greek, and later the book was translated into Latin during the Roman Empire. Due to his travels in the East, Alexander the Great collected the Indian epics "Avesta" and sent them to Greece. At that time, important books of the Avesta were also translated into Greek. Thanks to the translations, more and more teachings and great moral standards emerged and served the culture of humanity. In addition, translations gave a great impetus to the development of literary genres. In the years 593-574 BC, many sad songs of the prophets, which sang about the pain of separation, were translated into Greek and spread from there

to the borders of Europe. In the 19th century BC, David Ahangar's book of songs called "David Psalter" spread to the world through Greek and Latin translations. In the 4th-3rd centuries BC, the book "Song of Songs" by the prophet Suleiman had a strong influence on the creation of the entire European literature and the level of perception of the world and man. Thus, the first schools of translation were established in the museums (reading rooms) in Alexandria, just like the communities of scientists and philosophers in China and India, long before Christ. In them, prominent works on the history of world literature, literature, folklore, philosophy and other emerging fields of science were translated into Greek, Latin, ancient Arabic, Pahlavi languages, countries of the Mediterranean basin, Middle O The first book worlds and book treasures were created in the Middle East, China, India, and Tibet. On the one hand, translations made it possible to learn more deeply and better the sciences of various fields. Arabs from the middle of the 8th century AD

They started marching from the East to the Far West. They also entered the old Turan lands through Iran. In this process, Islamic teachings, Islamic law, Islamic culture and ways of living spread widely. Studying, memorizing, and believing in the Holy Qur'an in pure Arabic became a regular part of the educational life of the cities of Iran and Turan. In the 9th-12th centuries, science, philosophy, medicine, theology, literature, history, and folklore woke up in the land of Turan and started a new development path. Scholars such as Muhammad Musa Khorezmi, Farabi, Ibn Sina, Beruni, Qaffol Shoshi, Imam Bukhari, Imam Termizi, Zamakhshari, Najmuddin Kubro, Ahmed Yassavi, Suleiman Bakirghani, Farghani, who grew up in Movarounnahr, were not only engaged in science and their works brought a wave of new scientific views and inventions to the European continent thanks to the translation. These scientists from the Turanian regions were very interested in

translations, learning languages, and learning the cultures of other peoples. Nowadays, as we get acquainted with the field of translation, the development of every nation in the age of information or communication is definitely related to language. Interpreting has its own complexities. The reason is that it depends on the skill of the translator to express the spirit of the work of art in his native language, to choose the appropriate words or to find the equivalent options. No matter how well a translator knows a foreign language, if he is far from literature, he cannot understand the work and fully convey it to the reader. In addition, translators need to study sociolinguistics, ethnography and psycholinguistics. In the process of translation, the interpreter should notice the places that the reader did not see and reflect the meaning in it. Because it takes a lot of effort to revive a foreign way of life, its construction of sentences that are not characteristic of our language, and its purpose in Uzbek or another language. One of the shortcomings in the translation is that we turn English centuries into Uzbek through the Russian translation, which limits our ability to show the artistic spirit of the work in an alternative way. No matter in which language we translate, be it English or German, it is acceptable to translate from that language. Of course, it is natural to face cultural problems in translation. The reason is that the culture of each nation is reflected in its language. For example, the Japanese do not usually use the word "no". They use other words or phrases to avoid saying no. In Uzbekistan, the word "cotton" is used a lot, but this word is not used in Great Britain because cotton is not grown. Sometimes the words that are common to us may be unusual or, on the contrary, foreign to the representatives of other nations. Therefore, the translator compares not only two languages, but also two cultures.

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